

Advanced Parametric Modelling and Thermal Management System Optimization for More Electric Aircraft Using Nanofluids

The aerospace industry is embracing innovative technologies to enhance sustainability and performance, aligning with goals to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and meet the European Green Deal's climate-neutral objectives. As hybrid and electric propulsion systems gain prominence in aviation, the challenge of efficient thermal management becomes increasingly critical. This study focuses on developing a parametric model for designing a liquid-to-liquid Thermal Management System (TMS) for hybrid and electric aircraft, integrating both conventional and advanced coolants, including nanofluids. The model evaluates various thermal load conditions through simulations comparing water-antifreeze mixtures and nanofluids with varying nanoparticle types, concentrations, and fuel flow rates. Notably, the model identifies optimal TMS configurations for different mission profiles, including ground and ceiling conditions. The inclusion of nanofluids demonstrates significant potential for enhancing thermal performance and supporting sustainability goals by reducing CO₂ emissions. However, challenges such as nanoparticle agglomeration and system reliability must be addressed through further research. This work represents a meaningful advancement in optimizing TMS for electrified aircraft, with the potential to revolutionize aerospace thermal management through advanced coolant technologies.

Keywords: Thermal Management System, on design simulation, heat exchanger, nanofluids.

Nomenclature

A_{ff} = total free flow area, [m²]

A_{fr} = total frontal area, [m²]

b = plates distance, [m]

bf = base fluid

C_p = specific heat, [J/kg/K]

C_{min} = minimum heat capacity, [J/K]

D_h = hydraulic diameter, [m]

d = nanoparticle diameter, [m]

ε	= efficiency
f	= fanning friction factor
h	= fin height, [m]
j	= Coulburn factor
k	= thermal conductivity, [W/m/K]
K_B	= Boltzmann constant
l_f	= fin length (in the direction of flow), [m]
nf	= nanofluid
np	= nanoparticle
Nu	= Nusselt number
ΔP	= Pressure drop, [Pa]
p	= porosity
Pr	= Prandtl number
\dot{Q}	= heat output exchanged, [kW]
\dot{Q}_{max}	= maximum heat output that can be exchanged, [kW]
Re	= Reynolds number
s	= fin pitch (length transverse to the direction of flow), [m]
T	= mean temperature, [K]
t_f	= fin thickness, [m]
$T_{h,i}$	= inlet hot fluid Temperature, [K]
$T_{c,i}$	= inlet cold fluid Temperature, [K]

Greek symbol

β	= compactness degree
φ	= volumetric fraction
μ	= dynamic viscosity, [kg/m/s]
ρ	= density, [kg/m ³]

Acronyms

CPACS	= Common Parametric Aircraft Configuration Schema
EM	= Electric Motor
FOHE	= Fuel-Oil Heat Exchanger
HE - HX	= Heat Exchanger
ICAO	= International Civil Aviation Organization
LMTD	= Logarithmic Mean Temperature Difference
MEA	= More Electric Aircraft
NTU	= Number of Transfer Unit
OSF	= Offset Strip Fin
PAO	= Poly-Alpha-olifien Oil
PCM	= Phase Change Material
PEM	= Proton- Exchange Membrane
PFHE	= Plate and Fin Heat Exchanger
RFLP	= Requirements-Functional-Logical-Physical
SWCNT	= Single Walled Carbon NanoTube
TMS	= Thermal Management system

I. Introduction

The aerospace industry is undergoing a shifting phase marked by the integration of advanced technologies to enhance efficiency, sustainability, and performance. The International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) and the European Green Deal set ambitious targets to cut aviation emission achieve climate neutrality by 2050 [1]. These

initiatives drive regulatory measures, technological innovation, and international cooperation, fostering research in electric and hybrid aircraft as key solutions for long-term sustainability. In the last decades, the hybrid and electric propulsive systems have been gaining increasing interest to cut down greenhouse gas emissions and thus reduce the environment impact of the aerospace sector. In the aviation industry, cooling is a significant issue due to the high thermal load of new components of electrified or hybrid propulsive system. To reduce greenhouse gas emissions, improve fuel efficiency, and comply with stringent environmental regulations, aircraft systems become increasingly electrified and the demand for effective thermal management solutions has intensified. Achieving these sustainability goals requires innovative approaches to managing the heat generated by advanced electrical systems and components. So, a crucial area driving this transformation is the development and optimization of thermal management systems (TMS).

The TMS is designed to ensure and manage the temperature control of various equipment within the aircraft. The TMS presents a significant challenge for next-generation hybrid or all-electric aircraft [2]. Unlike conventional combustion engines, these systems generate low-grade heat, characterized by lower temperature heat flows and an inability to use combustion gases for heat dissipation. This scenario demands innovative approaches to TMS to ensure efficient and effective heat dissipation from critical components. Addressing this challenge is essential for maintaining the performance, reliability, and safety of electrified aircraft. Effective thermal management strategies must be developed to handle these low-grade heat sources to ensure the optimal performance and longevity of the propulsion system.

Conventional cooling techniques, including air and liquid cooling, are becoming insufficient for addressing these thermal challenges because of their limited thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity. This limitation has generated a growing interest in innovative cooling technologies, particularly the use of nanofluids. Nanofluids [3], engineered colloidal suspensions of nanoparticles within a base fluid, offer a promising solution for enhancing the thermal performance of aerospace cooling systems. The incorporation of nanoparticles can significantly improve the thermal conductivity and convective heat transfer properties of the base fluid, resulting in more efficient heat dissipation. Although the concept dates back to the late 1800s, research on nanofluids has surged in the past two decades. By dispersing nanoparticles (typically <1% concentration, <100 nm diameter) in base fluids, nanofluids enhance thermal conductivity while minimizing deposition and obstruction of the coolant flow. Common nanoparticles include metal oxides, carbides, nitrides, and carbon-based materials, while base fluids range from water

and glycols to oils and bio-fluids. Their thermal performance depends on a trade-off between increased conductivity and higher viscosity. Despite the generally stable dispersion of nanoparticles in nanofluids, experimental studies highlight concerns regarding settling phenomena and stability, particularly influenced by preparation methods. Safety considerations regarding nanotechnologies, in particular their potential environmental and health impacts, remain of primary importance. Adequate research is essential to balance the benefits of nanoparticles with potential risks, emphasizing the importance of adopting green, non-toxic, and biodegradable nanoparticles for sustainable industrial applications, especially in biomedicine.

In recent years, significant progress has been made in TMS development, with numerous studies exploring various architectures involving fuel systems, heat exchanger design optimization, and nanofluid applications. Coutinho et al. [4] conducted an analysis focusing on the latest advancements in TMS solutions for hybrid-electric aircraft. According to their findings, incorporating fuel as a heat sink within a hybrid electric propulsion system is a feasible strategy. This method reuses waste heat for necessary thermal applications, specifically by preheating the fuel before combustion. This approach enhances energy management and mitigates the negative impact on efficiency. Gkoutzamanis et al. [5] reported a correlation between TMS design, selected propulsive configuration and energy management, through a weight estimation of TMS for hybrid propulsion concepts aircraft. Through OpenConcept tool, the integration of mission performance and sizing tool, with thermal analysis and parametric cost, are estimated. Kellermann et al. [6] explored fuel as primary heat sink in future hybrid-electric aircraft. By evaluating the thermal demands in all phases of a mission analysis, they identified the end of cruise and the top of climb points as the most demanding phases. Wang et al. [7] investigated the thermal management technologies to control and optimize heat distribution and dissipation. Their study discussed the role of fuel tanks as heat sinks, where the fuel absorbs excess heat generated by other systems, thereby assisting in the overall thermal management and enhancing energy efficiency. Alyanak and Allison [8] explore the integration of a fuel thermal management system (FTMS) during the conceptual design phase of aircraft sizing. By analysing the thermal loads and performance constraints, the research highlights how the FTMS can effectively utilize fuel as a heat sink to manage waste heat from onboard systems. The findings demonstrate that incorporating FTMS considerations early in the design process significantly improves overall system efficiency and ensures compliance with thermal and operational requirements.

Reed et al. [9] , Saltzman et al. [10] , Staley et al. [11] and NASA report [12] focus on the optimization of the geometry of heat exchanger. William C. Reed et al. [9] evaluate various heat exchanger and thermal energy storage

designs for aircraft thermal management systems, focusing on their performance, weight, and integration challenges. The study provides insights into optimizing thermal management solutions to meet the stringent requirements of modern aircraft. Andrew Saltzman et al. [10] compares the performance of conventionally manufactured and additively manufactured heat exchangers used in aircraft. It assesses factors such as thermal efficiency, pressure drop, and structural integrity, highlighting the potential benefits and challenges of additive manufacturing in aerospace thermal management applications. The NATO publication [11] discusses the aerothermal design considerations for integrating thermal management systems within aircraft engines and vehicles. It explores the use of heat exchangers and other components to effectively manage thermal loads, emphasizing the importance of system-level integration and optimization. The NASA report, [12], discusses the development of a thermal management system for electrified aircraft, emphasizing the use of liquid-cooled systems. It details the design considerations for heat exchangers that utilize fuel as a coolant, aiming to efficiently manage heat generated by electrical components.

Previous studies have assessed TMS designs in relation to heat load sensitivity [13]. This work investigates the design of TMS specifically for electrified aircraft propulsion systems, focusing on their response to varying thermal loads. Through simulations of different operating conditions across the mission profile, the study identifies key design parameters required to maintain reliable performance under fluctuating heat dissipation demands. The results demonstrate that a heat load-sensitive TMS can enhance system robustness and adaptability, minimizing thermal constraints during different phases of the mission.

Different studies analyse the impact of mission condition on TMS development. Brelje et al. [14] develops a conceptual-level model for a liquid-based TMS designed for electrified aircraft propulsion. The study focuses on cooling circuits that transfer heat from electrical components to heat exchangers across the aircraft, accounting for variations in the mission profile. The results highlight the importance of integrating TMS design with mission-specific operating conditions, demonstrating that such an approach can optimize thermal performance while minimizing system weight and drag.

According to literature [3], nanofluids can be used as coolants, replacing existing coolants in systems with high heat-dissipation requirements, through their improved heat transfer performance [3]. Tao et al. [15] examined nanofluids compared to conventional coolants for Fuel Cell Vehicles, highlighting how the use of nanofluids can lead to more efficient thermal management systems in fuel cell vehicles. Improved cooling efficiency can enhance the overall performance and longevity of fuel cells, reducing energy consumption and improving the reliability and

durability of these vehicles. Experimental findings support the notion that nanofluids can reduce the radiator size while enhancing heat dissipation capabilities. [16] investigates the application of nanofluids in the thermal management systems of electric vehicle battery cooling modules. Through computational analysis, it evaluates the temperature distribution and pressure drop within the cooling modules. The findings demonstrate that a single nanofluid significantly enhances thermal management performance by improving heat transfer efficiency compared to conventional coolants, thereby supporting more compact and efficient system designs.

The aim of this work is to develop a sizing model of TMS to address the sustainability challenges, to obtain adequate lightweighted equipment and to investigate using several innovative coolants. This work delves into the principles and benefits of nanofluids, exploring their potential to revolutionize thermal management in the context of electrified aerospace systems.

The paper further explores the preliminary research reported by Caggese et al. [17]. This study concerns the development of a parametric model to design and size the TMS of more electric and hybrid electric aircraft. The selection of the design point as a crucial aspect of TMS design prompts this paper to investigate Take-Off and Ceiling conditions. This investigation aims to appropriately size the TMS and to account for the thermal demands under worst-case scenarios. Moreover, environmental conditions significantly affect the overall performance of the cooling systems. Hot-day conditions impose the most severe demands on the TMS.

Unlike previous studies, which often focus on single coolants or generalized thermal management approaches, this paper introduces a parametric model capable of evaluating and directly comparing multiple coolant options, including conventional water-antifreeze mixtures and advanced nanofluids. The model's ability to simulate varying nanoparticle concentrations and analyse their impacts on system performance (such as heat exchanger mass and volume optimization) offers a level of granularity not previously explored in comparable works. Furthermore, this study investigates the trade-offs between increased fuel inlet flow rates and pump power requirements, providing valuable insights into system-level design choices. By quantifying the environmental benefits of reduced CO₂ emissions alongside technical performance metrics, this work also aligns closely with the aviation sector's sustainability goals, representing a significant advancement over existing TMS studies.

II. Methodology

A. TMS – Architecture definition

The TMS can employ various cooling techniques, including liquid cooling methods. Figure 1 depicts the schematic of the liquid-to-liquid architecture, composed of two cooling line modules:

- Main cooling module that involves the coolant loop
- Secondary cooling module that involves the fuel loop

As a parametric model, it allows the investigation of several heat sources and varying thermal demands.

Figure 1 Schema for architecture of liquid cooling system.

In aerospace applications, compact heat exchangers are preferred for their small volume and enhanced surface area, achieved through fins or laminations. The selected heat exchanger employs fin surfaces in an unmixed crossflow configuration, optimizing heat exchange between fluids with different thermal properties. Advanced manufacturing enables their use with various materials, high temperatures, and pressures. Among compact designs, counterflow and crossflow configurations in plate and fin heat exchangers offer the best efficiency at a given NTU [18]. The chosen design features an Offset Strip-type geometry, also known as Serrated or Interrupted Fin.

The proposed methodology is based on the V-Model for Systems Engineering, employing the requirements-functional-logical-physical (RFLP) modelling approach for system decomposition [19].

In particular, it is focused on the mathematical modelling of the TMS through the development of a parametric sizing script within a Python environment. The study is primarily dedicated to the heat exchanger, that can be considered the core component of the TMS, by developing a parametric sizing model for an Offset Strip Fin (OSF) surface heat exchanger (HX). The choice of OSF heat exchanger combines the advantages of Plate & Fin designs, such as compactness and increased heat exchange surface area, with reduced pressure losses [20]. The sizing algorithm for the heat exchanger, that will be described later, is integrated into the overall algorithm for the TMS design, ensuring

comprehensive sizing of all TMS components. Input data are provided by a .xml file, specifically a Common Parametric Aircraft Configuration Schema (CPACS) file [21], which includes aircraft details, mission parameters, heat source specifications, environmental conditions, and heat exchanger type, among others. Similarly, all output data are stored in an output CPACS file, facilitating integration with other design disciplines. The aim of the TMS design algorithm is to size the TMS equipment under various design conditions. The primary objective of the HX sizing algorithm is to achieve convergence towards the design temperature as defined by the heat source requirements by iteratively increasing the initial size of the heat exchanger and its fin heat transfer. Figure 2 depicts a simplified flow chart of the sizing workflow and the main input and output data.

Figure 2 Workflow sizing script.

The model formulation presented in this study develops upon the research and data compiled by references [18] and [19]. Specifically, the TMS design employs the ϵ -NTU method [20] to determine the appropriate size of the heat exchanger, utilizing parameters such as the coolant inlet temperature, thermal load demand, and heat exchanger characteristics. The integration of this methodology into the model provides a robust framework for accurately sizing heat exchangers under diverse operating conditions, thereby enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of thermal management systems.

B. Heat exchanger mathematical model

The ε -NTU methodology allows for solving the heat exchanger analysis by determining the fluid outlet temperatures given the known inlet temperatures, flow rates, and defined exchanger type. The efficiency (ε) is a dimensionless parameter defined as:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\dot{Q}}{\dot{Q}_{max}} = \frac{\text{heat output actually exchanged}}{\text{maximum heat output that can be exchanged}} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where \dot{Q} represents the actual heat transfer rate and \dot{Q}_{max} represents the maximum exchangeable thermal power. Without knowing the outlet temperatures of the fluids from the heat exchanger and deriving the effectiveness from the relations linking it to the type of geometry, it is possible to derive the heat capacity exchanged:

$$\dot{Q} = \varepsilon \dot{Q}_{max} = \varepsilon C_{min}(T_{h,i} - T_{c,i}) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

It is possible to relate this formulation back to the number of NTU heat exchange units from the correlation between ε -NTU and the capacity ratio C^* as defined in the following equation.

$$C^* = C_{min} / C_{max} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Hence:

$$\varepsilon = f(NTU, C^*) = f\left(\frac{UA}{C_{min}}, \frac{C_{min}}{C_{max}}\right), \text{ where} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$NTU = \frac{UA}{C_{min}} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

The type of heat exchanger flow arrangement differentiates this correlation. In the compact heat exchangers, the two fluids generally flow in mutually perpendicular directions. This flow configuration is referred to as crossflow.

Crossflow (unmixed):
$$\varepsilon = 1 - \exp\left\{\frac{NTU^{-0.22}}{C^*} \left[\exp(-C^*NTU^{0.78}) - 1\right]\right\} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

Typical aerospace solutions employ compact heat exchangers, such as plate or plate and fin surface heat exchangers. Plate and fin heat exchangers (PFHEs) are particularly notable among compact heat exchangers due to their design incorporating secondary surfaces or internal ducts between layers. This design increases the exchange surface area and reduces hydraulic diameters.

The mathematical model of the heat exchanger is divided into two subsections:

- Geometrical correlations: based on the selected type of heat exchanger, specifically the Offset Strip Fin (OSF) heat exchanger.

- Heat transfer correlations: based on heat transfer for a liquid-to-liquid heat exchanger.

1. Geometrical correlations

The following discussion defines the correlations due to the offset strip internal geometry, visually represented by the geometrical parameters depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Geometrical schema of Offset Strip Fin (OSF) Heat Exchanger. [22] , [19]

Table 1 Dimensionless parameters of OSF Heat Exchanger.

Offset Strip Fin	
Aspect ratio	Correlation
α	s/h Eq. 7
δ	t_f/l_f Eq. 8
γ	t_f/s Eq. 9

The calculation of the hydraulic diameter considers the lateral and vertical geometry of the ducts.

$$D_h = \frac{4 s h l}{[2(s l + h l + t_f h) + t_f s]} \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

Porosity, p , defined as void volume/total volume ratio, gives an indication of the weight of the heat exchanger core:

$$p = \frac{s(b - t_f)}{(s - t_f)(b + t)} = \frac{s h}{(s - t_f)(b + t)} \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

The parameter β (defined in Eq.) distinguishes a compact heat exchanger from a non-compact one, providing an indication of the density of the exchange area. The reference values given in the literature, [20] and [24] , identify a compact liquid-to-liquid heat exchanger if β takes values greater than 400 [m²/m³], whereas if gases are involved, it must be greater than 700 [m²/m³].

$$\beta = \frac{4p}{D_h} \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

To finalize the geometrical characteristics, it is necessary to evaluate the areas, and particularly the exchange area. The heat transfer area is the total of the exchange areas of the ducts, formulated by Maiti and Sarangi [25], for Offset Strip Fins surface:

$$A_s = 2hl_f + 2ht_f + 2sl_f \quad \text{Heat transfer area / fin} \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

$$A = \frac{A_s p_f W L N_{finlayer}}{l_f} \quad \text{Total heat transfer area} \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

And for the determination of the free flow area, A_{ff} , the ratio of free flow to frontal area of one side of exchanger, σ , is introduced:

$$\sigma = \frac{h(s - t_f)}{(s + t_f)(h + t_f)} \quad \text{Eq. 15}$$

$$A_{ff} = \sigma A_{fr} = \sigma b N_{finlayers} W \quad \text{Eq. 16}$$

2. Heat transfer correlations

Once the geometric parameters are defined, the flow characteristics are evaluated through Reynolds and Prandtl numbers [20]. As this is a liquid-liquid heat exchanger, the heat transfer coefficient is derived from the Nusselt number, determined using interpolation for laminar flow and the Gnielinski correlation for turbulent flow [18]. Due to limited data on Offset Strip Fin (OSF) heat exchangers with liquid cooling, existing correlations—often developed for air or gases—may not fully capture liquid behavior, especially given the significantly higher Prandtl numbers of fluids like water and PAO [26], [27]. Experimental studies [23], [26], [28], [31], have reported deviations of $\pm 10\text{--}30\%$ in heat transfer predictions and up to $\pm 25\%$ for friction factor estimates. Numerical simulations on 18 OSF geometries [30] confirmed accuracy within $\pm 20\%$ in most cases, though errors up to 50% were observed for certain configurations. Table 2 summarizes the main correlations used and their expected error margins, providing a practical reference for heat transfer estimation in liquid-cooled systems.

Table 2: Fanning friction factor and Colburn coefficient.

Marglik e Bergles, $120 < Re < 10^4$:	
$f = 9.6243 Re^{-0.7442} \alpha^{-0.1856} \delta^{0.3053} \gamma^{-0.2659} (1 + 7.669 * 10^{-8} Re^{4.429} \alpha^{0.92} \delta^{3.767} \gamma^{0.236})^{0.1}$	Eq. 17
$j = 0.6522 Re^{-0.504} \alpha^{-0.1541} \delta^{-0.1409} \gamma^{-0.0678} (1 + 5.269 * 10^{-5} Re^{1.34} \alpha^{0.504} \delta^{0.456} \gamma^{-1.055})^{0.1}$	Eq. 18
Blasius, $10^4 < Re < 10^5$:	
$f = 0.0791 Re^{-0.25}$	Eq. 19
$j = St Pr^{-2/3} = 0.664 Re^{-0.5} Pr^{-2/3}$	Eq. 20

Wieting, $Re < 10^3$:

$$f = 7.661 \left(\frac{l_f}{D_h} \right)^{-0.384} \alpha^{-0.092} Re^{-0.712} \quad \text{Eq. 21}$$

$$j = 0.483 \left(\frac{l_f}{D_h} \right)^{-0.162} \alpha^{-0.184} Re^{-0.536} \quad \text{Eq. 22}$$

Wieting, $Re > 2 * 10^3$:

$$f = 1.136 \left(\frac{l_f}{D_h} \right)^{-0.781} \left(\frac{t_f}{D_h} \right)^{-0.534} Re^{-0.198} \quad \text{Eq. 23}$$

$$j = 0.242 \left(\frac{l_f}{D_h} \right)^{-0.322} \left(\frac{t_f}{D_h} \right)^{0.08} Re^{-0.368} \quad \text{Eq. 24}$$

Having evaluated the Nusselt number as function of the flow regime, the equation that determines the heat transfer coefficient in the case of liquid fluid is as follows:

$$h = \frac{Nu k_{fluid}}{D_h} \quad \text{Eq. 25}$$

Finally, the overall conductance U is evaluated for both hot and cold side, where A_c and A_h are used to identify the heat transfer surfaces of the cold side and the hot side, respectively [20].

In the initial discussion, a heat exchanger at the beginning of its operational life is assumed, with no fouling present affecting its performance. Generally, the accumulation of deposits on the exchange surfaces reduces heat transfer due to additional resistance. Typical values of thermal resistance due to fouling can be incorporated into the conductance formulation to obtain a comprehensive expression of the phenomenon. Additional factors that contribute to performance degradation include corrosion and chemical fouling processes, which are also introduced through the fouling factor (Eq. 26).

Considering all possible contributions, the general expression of overall conductance is:

$$U = \sum R_{heat\ transfer}, R_{wall}, R_{convection}, R_{other} \quad \text{Eq. 26}$$

NTU correlations remain to be introduced:

$$NTU_{max} = \frac{UA}{C_{min}} \quad \text{Eq. 27}$$

Once the number of total heat exchange units has been calculated, it is possible to derive the number of heat exchange units for the individual side:

$$NTU = \frac{2NTU_{max}}{\eta_f} \quad \text{Eq. 28}$$

Defining the fin efficiency, η_f :

$$\eta_f = \frac{\tanh(ml)}{ml} \quad \text{Eq. 29}$$

by explicating

$$m = \sqrt{\frac{2h}{k_m t_f} \left(1 + \frac{t_f}{l_f}\right)} \quad \text{Eq. 30}$$

Finally, knowing the Number of Transfer Units (NTU) formulations, it is possible to calculate the effectiveness ε of the selected type of heat exchanger:

$$\varepsilon = 1 - \exp\left\{\frac{NTU^{-0.22}}{C^*} \left[\exp(-C^* NTU^{0.78}) - 1\right]\right\} \quad \text{Eq. 31}$$

In the following section, the introduced formulations are applied to the sizing model.

C. Sizing model

This section explores the heat exchanger model developed in Python environment. The script is capable of interfacing with a dedicated XML-based data format, namely the CPACS [21]. This format is used to describe aircraft characteristics and their corresponding data, providing and saving the sizing script's input and output, respectively.

The model focuses on the development of the heat exchanger and the primary components of the TMS. The heat sources to be cooled provide information on the heat load to be dissipated, along with key requirements such as the maximum allowable fluid inlet temperature and the minimum mass flow rate. This information is automatically generated from the CPACS file. The system is modelled for the design point without considering off-design conditions. Additionally, the solution is developed for steady-state conditions, assuming long periods with no change in operating conditions. Therefore, fluid flow rates, as well as velocities and temperatures at the inlet and outlet, can be considered constant. Initially, the model establishes a one-to-one relationship between the thermal source and the heat exchanger.

The proposed model employs three iterations loops, detailed in Figure 4:

- An external loop for the convergence of the HX outlet temperature;
- An intermediate loop for the optimisation of the free flow area;

- An inner loop for the optimisation of the inner core duct height.

Figure 4 Detailed heat exchanger sizing model.

In this way, depending on the maximization of duct efficiency, the internal geometry suitable to meet the application's needs is found. Fin efficiency is exploited to derive a new value of h and optimize the core. After optimizing the internal geometry, the convergence between the initially estimated free flow area from the geometry and the free flow area obtainable from the mass velocity is further refined. Once convergence on these values is achieved, the final step is to iterate until the constraint on the output temperature is satisfied.

Delving into the model, the type of heat exchanger, geometry, and flow arrangement are first defined, as these are crucial to the expressions used. The geometric parameters and their correlations are based on: 1. Geometrical

correlations to ensure convergence on temperature; 2. *Heat transfer correlations*, it is necessary to iteratively increase the overall dimensions of the exchanger, equally in the two spatial dimensions (length and width) and by adding additional layers. In this way, the exchanger grows iteratively in all three spatial dimensions.

The model iterates the inner loop until convergence on the outlet temperature is achieved. Once the resolution of the heat exchanger is completed, the outputs of the heat exchanger can be determined. Aerospace applications have volume and mass constraints that must be met, making it crucial to estimate the mass and volume occupied by the exchanger. The volume is determined by three spatial dimensions; however, for model simplification, at each iteration one dimension is kept fixed, while the other two vary according to the internal optimization of the ducts.

$$\mathbf{Volume = Length * Width * Height} \quad \mathbf{Eq. 32}$$

The number of layers can be estimated from the height (H). Weight, on the other hand, takes into account the internal arrangement of the ducts, the material density, the free flow area, A_{ff} , and the ratio of free flow to frontal area.

$$\mathbf{Weight = \rho_m L \left(\frac{A_{ff,1}}{\sigma_1} (1 - \sigma_1) + \frac{A_{ff,2}}{\sigma_2} (1 - \sigma_2) \right)} \quad \mathbf{Eq. 33}$$

The volume occupied by the fins and ducts is determined by the free flow area and porosity, which accounts for the solid material volume, excluding the free flow regions. By multiplying the effective volume by the material density, the weight contribution from each side can be calculated. The total weight is then obtained by summing the contributions from both sides.

To integrate the heat exchanger into the remaining TMS, it is necessary to estimate the pressure drop, which indicates the pressure that must be supplied by the pump for full circuit operation:

$$\Delta P = \left(\frac{m_{in}}{A_{ff}} \right)^2 \frac{4fL}{2\rho_{fluid}D_h} \quad \mathbf{Eq. 34}$$

Muzychka et al. [34] discussed the influence of geometrical parameters of the internal ducts in heat exchangers on pressure drops by analysing the following fin parameters: s , l , h , and t . They demonstrated that increasing the cross-sectional pitch of the fins reduces pressure drop by increasing the flow area and reducing flow resistance. Conversely, decreasing fin length introduces higher pressure drops and reduces heat transfer performance, as it does not allow the thermal field to develop fully. Duct height has no significant influence on pressure drop for liquid working fluids; however, an increase in duct height creates a larger free flow area, which, similar to an increased transverse pitch, results in a reduction in pressure drop. The last geometric parameter discussed is fin thickness. Increased fin thickness

hinders the free passage of liquid, reducing the free flow area and consequently increasing pressure drop. This discussion aids in the selection of geometric characteristics of the surface, considering their implications on pressure drops.

From the pressure drop, it is possible to derive the mass velocity:

$$G = \sqrt{\frac{2\rho_{fluid}\Delta P j/f}{Pr^{2/3} NTU}} \quad \text{Eq. 35}$$

In this case, the heat exchanger's spatial dimensions, final weight, final volume, outlet fluid temperatures, core pressure drops, system electric consumption, distribution pipe characteristics, and overall TMS weight are saved in the CPACS output file. Otherwise, the script increases the initial size of the heat exchanger and restarts the iterative loop.

D. Nanofluid modelling

Nanofluids are investigated to improve the heat transfer performance of heat exchangers due to their promising thermophysical properties. It is essential to highlight that thermal management in hybrid-electric aircraft represents a particularly critical challenge due to the high thermal loads and compact system design. The use of nanofluids could significantly contribute to the feasibility of an efficient TMS, underscoring one of the distinctive aspects of this research.

The behaviour of nanofluids is influenced by several factors (volume fraction of nanoparticles, particle size, specific type of nanoparticles employed, methods of preparation). Each of these variables plays a crucial role in determining the thermal performance and stability of the resulting nanofluid, highlighting the importance of systematic investigation and optimization in nanofluid development for effective heat transfer enhancement.

In their study, Das et al. [3] examined various formulations used to describe the thermophysical properties essential for modelling nanofluids. For optimal performance, a low nanoparticle concentration, typically below 1%, is preferred. This minimizes issues such as deposits, fouling, or flowing in narrow ducts.

To aid the selection of suitable nanofluids for heat exchanger applications, a nanoparticle database has been compiled. This database allows users to select the type of nanoparticles and base fluid, and to determine the level of dispersion. The database includes commonly studied nanoparticles in both theoretical and experimental research.

Table 3 summarizes the thermophysical properties of selected nanoparticles at temperature of 25 °C.

Table 3 Thermophysical properties of nanoparticle database.

Nanoparticle	Density [kg/m ³]	Thermal capacity [J/kgK]	Thermal conductivity [W/mK]
Al ₂ O ₃	3950	850	25
CuO	6320	550	33
ZnO	5610	430	13
Ag	10490	240	407
TiO ₂	4230	680	8.4
SWCNT	2170	2100	3000
Cu	8960	380	395
SiO ₂	2650	930	1.4

The most commonly used base fluids are water, ethylene glycol or propylene glycol mixtures with water, ethylene glycol, R141b, and R11. The properties of these fluids are initialized in the model using the CoolProp library [33], which allows for their evaluation at different temperatures. Once the inputs are selected, the database, integrated into the Thermal Management System model, enables the evaluation of the model's final performance to determine which nanofluid has the greatest impact on the application.

The thermophysical equations of the nanofluid model is based on the work *Nanofluids, Science and technology*, Das [et al.] (Ref. [3]).

The density is defined as:

$$\rho_{nf} = f_v \rho_{np} + (1 - f_v) \rho_{bf} \quad \text{Eq. 36}$$

Regarding heat capacity, current research indicates that nanofluids have a lower heat capacity compared to the base fluids involved. It is defined as:

$$c_{p,nf} = \frac{f_v \rho_{np} c_{p,np} + (1 - f_v) \rho_{bf} c_{p,bf}}{\rho_{nf}} \quad \text{Eq. 37}$$

Thermal conductivity is a fundamental thermophysical property for interpreting the performance of the liquid under investigation. It is defined as:

$$k_{nf} = k_{bf} \frac{k_{np} + 2 k_{bf} + 2(k_{np} - k_{bf})f_v}{k_{np} + 2 k_{bf} - (k_{np} - k_{bf})f_v} \quad \text{Eq. 38}$$

The viscosity of nanofluids is generally higher than base fluids, influenced by the type and concentration of particles. It is defined as:

$$\mu_{nf} = \mu_{bf}(1 + 2.5f_v) \quad \text{Eq. 39}$$

The volumetric fraction:

$$f_v = \frac{V_{np}}{V_{np} + V_{bf}} \approx \frac{V_{np}}{V_{bf}} \quad \text{Eq. 40}$$

Integrating the database into the parametric model of the TMS paves the way for future investigative developments aimed at creating more compact and high-performance systems. Nanofluids possess unique thermal properties that have the potential to reduce the need for larger heat exchangers and increased frontal areas, thereby enabling the design of smaller radiators.

III. Results

A. Validation of ϵ -NTU method

The adopted model of ϵ -NTU method is validated by comparison with a compact, liquid-liquid heat exchanger presented in the literature [18]. The case study provides the temperatures of the two fluids at the outlet, allowing direct calculation of the effectiveness and compliance with the outlet temperature conditions. The validation model adheres to the formulations previously mentioned and the results obtained are tabulated, Table 4, showing the percentage error compared to the literature case.

Table 4 Comparison of reference case [18] and sizing model output.

OUTPUT	Error %
Outlet Temperature Side 1	0.07
Outlet Temperature Side 2	2.4
ϵ (Counterflow)	-1.2
NTU	-0.04

B. Geometric model validation

To validate the heat exchanger geometry in the sizing model, a comparison is made with an offset fins heat exchanger from the literature [35]. The experimental results from [35] provide insights into a compact liquid-to-liquid heat exchanger. Understanding the geometrical characteristics of this device facilitates the validation of the equations outlined in Section 1 *Geometrical correlations*. The test core corresponds to a compact heat exchanger with an Offset Strip Fin design and a crossflow arrangement. The inner core geometry, along with other relevant model inputs, is detailed in Table 5. The material used for construction is Aluminium AA-6061. The experimental setup involves a heat exchanger with dimensions of 0.15 [m] x 0.15 [m] x 0.020 [m]. To minimize heat loss to the external environment, two layers of ducts are utilized for the cold side, while only one layer is employed for the hot side.

Table 5 Performance and geometry input of the reference heat exchanger from [35]

INPUT	Unit	Hot side	Cold side
Fluid	[-]	Water	Water

INPUT	Unit	Hot side	Cold side
Inlet Temperature	[°C]	60	25
Volumetric flow rate	[lpm]	3	10
Geometric parameters			
Type of fin	[-]	Offset	Offset
Fin frequency	[PFI]	28	28
Fin height	[mm]	5.5	5.5
Fin thickness	[mm]	0.127	0.127
Serration length	[mm]	3.175	3.175
Flow length	[m]	0.15	0.15
N. of layers	[-]	1	2
Material	[-]	Aluminium AA-6061	

The validation in this instance is not primarily about the thermodynamic resolution method, but rather focuses on the geometric formulas of the heat exchanger and the resulting performance. Since the geometry employed in the experimental tests is known, validation of the expressions for calculating the exchange area and hydraulic diameter is attainable.

Table 6 Performance and geometrical output comparison between reference case [35] and sizing model.

OUTPUT	Experimental case [35]			Measured value			
	Fluid	Unit	Side hot	Side cold	Side hot	Error %	Side cold
Hydraulic diameter	[m]	0.001345	0.001345	0.0013	-2.36	0.0013	-2.36
Total heat transfer area	[m ²]	0.158	0.316	0.1579	-0.033	0.3159	-0.033
Pressure Drop	[Pa]	650		638,59	-1.75		

C. On-design model: TEST CASE

The reference aircraft is an 80-seat turboprop designed by HERA [36] project.

Two configurations are developed:

- Baseline: a regional Turboprop
- Innovative: a hybrid-electric aircraft powered by fuel cell.

The baseline configuration represents a conventional architecture with two standard turboprop engine, while the innovative configuration features a parallel hybrid propulsion architecture. In this design, the electric motor is powered by a hydrogen fuel cell, supplemented by a buffer battery to support the peak load demands and emergency. HERA aims to achieve a 50% reduction in technology-based GHG emissions. The Thermal Management System (TMS) must dissipate the heat produced by the electric motor, inverter, and fuel cell, which are critical heat sources.

As part of the trade-off study, an alternative architecture is here proposed. It includes a liquid-to-liquid heat exchanger located in the engine nacelle, designed to dissipate heat from the electric motor and its inverter. The heat exchanger operates with two different liquids: the primary loop absorbs heat from the heat source and transfers it to

the secondary liquid, which is the fuel. The fuel, acting as the working fluid in the secondary loop, dissipating heat through the wing tanks to the external environment. Initially cold, the fuel reaches higher temperatures in the tank after the heat exchange process.

Figure 5 Liquid cooling system architecture.

The tank requirements are determined based on the findings of reference [37], which conducted a Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) analysis of the tank and its fuel content, examining temperature variations with altitude. In that study, an ambient temperature of 15 °C was assumed, not an ISA deviation (i.e., not ISA + 15 °C). To adopt a conservative approach in assessing the take-off test case, the fuel tank system's temperature is instead assumed to be in thermal equilibrium with the surrounding environment, rather than relying solely on the fixed 15 °C condition used in reference [37].

Five test cases are designed to assess the operation of the liquid-liquid heat exchanger under varying degrees of hybridization, reflecting progressive reductions in carbon dioxide emissions due to the increased electric motor power output at the expense of conventional propulsion. The five evaluated test cases are shown in Table 7:

Table 7 Sizing model input for 5 different test cases [17]

	Thermal power [kW]		TMS coolant mass flow [kg/s]	
	Ground	Ceiling	Ground	Ceiling
Test case 1	14.3	14.3	0.136	0.136
Test case 2	28.3	28.3	0.270	0.270
Test case 3	41.2	41.2	0.393	0.393
Test case 4	54.2	54.2	0.517	0.517
Test case 5	67.2	67.2	0.641	0.641

The Ground condition, equivalent to the Take-Off condition, occurs at sea level with a conservative Δ ISA of +20 °C. The Ceiling condition, FL250, represents an altitude of 7620 m with a Δ ISA of +20 °C. The mass flow rates of

the coolant liquid are set as inputs to ensure adequate cooling, varying according to each test case. Initially, a coolant mixture of water and 40% antifreeze is considered, but the potential application of nanofluids is also evaluated due to their promising features. The coolant temperature at the outlet of the electric motor is assumed to be 90 °C, matching the inlet temperature of the heat exchanger. It is assumed that no heat transfer occurs in the distribution system,. Similarly, the coolant liquid temperature at the outlet of the heat exchanger must converge to 65 °C, as this is the constraint defined for the coolant temperature at the inlet of the inverter.

Figure 6 Inlet and outlet coolant temperature requirements.

These two temperatures serve as the inlet and outlet temperatures of the heat exchanger loop containing the coolant liquid, aligning with state-of-the-art standards documented in the literature [38]. The inlet and outlet temperatures for the second loop involving fuel are determined based on [37]. However, for the ground condition, a more conservative scenario is considered, where the tank is not refuelled immediately before take-off, allowing it to reach thermal equilibrium with the environment (excluding solar radiation). This approach adopts a baseline temperature that is +15 °C higher than the value reported in the [37]. The fuel outlet temperature at the heat exchanger is not explicitly constrained, as long as it remains below the flammability limit and does not fall below -45 °C. In addition to the predefined TMS parameters of the initial architecture, the coordinates of the heat sink, represented by the wing fuel tanks, must be accounted for. It is assumed that the fuel travels 80% of the wing's half-span, as the tanks do not extend to the wingtip. Simulations are conducted with the fuel inlet flow rate set to ensure the disposal of the required thermal power. The chosen heat exchanger is an offset strip fin compact heat exchanger with a crossflow arrangement, enabling the two fluids to flow perpendicular to each other without mixing. In each iteration, the model adjusts the width and length incrementally, adding two layers in the vertical direction—one for hot fluid flow and one for cold fluid flow. The third dimension is increased only when the Reynolds number exceeds 200, in order to avoid operation at excessively low Reynolds values. For each proposed condition, the outputs include efficiency, pressure drop, fuel flow, mass, volume, and three overall dimensional quantities. The mass parameter exclusively accounts for the metal structure of the heat exchanger, excluding the mass of the liquids occupying the interstices.

Table 8 Simulation Parameters.

Parameters	Unit	Ground (TO)	Ceiling (FL250)
Altitude	[m]	0	7620
Delta ISA	[-]	+20	+20
Coolant	[-]	Water - 40% Ethylene Glycol	Water - 40% Ethylene Glycol
Coolant inlet temperature - Inverter	[°C]	65	65
Coolant outlet temperature – Electric motor	[°C]	90	90
Pipe roughness	[mm]	0.02	0.02
Maximum recommended fluid velocity	[m/s]	2.5	2.5
Number of curves at 90°	[-]	4	4
(Heat exchanger - Heat source) coordinate	[x, y, z]	[0.5; 0; 1]	[0.5; 0; 1]
heat-source pressure drop	[bar]	1	1
heat source coolant capacity	[l]	3	3
Pump efficiency	[-]	0.7	0.7
Motor efficiency	[-]	0.9	0.9
Mass Power ratio (electric motor and pump)	[kg/kW]	16	16

The analysis is carried out using a conventional cooling liquid and one which includes nanoparticles. Simulations are conducted under identical conditions for both the coolant loop and the fuel module. Figure 7 and Figure 8 depict the main model output at the five level of thermal power for ground and ceiling condition, comparing the water-antifreeze mixture with Al₂O₃ nanofluid. The results of the heat exchanger modelling, including the associated thermal management system (TMS), reveal a linear trend in the performance metrics across the evaluated conditions, as depicted in the accompanying graphs. The sizing point for the system is identified under the ground condition at the highest heat dissipation demand scenario (test case 5).

Figure 7 Sizing model Output - TMS mass at different thermal power level using EG40W60 (a) and 0.502% Al₂O₃-EG40W60 (b), at Ground and Ceiling condition.

Figure 8 Sizing model Output – HE Volume at different thermal power level using EG40W60 (a) and 0.502% Al₂O₃- EG40W60 (b), at Ground and Ceiling condition.

The overall mass of the TMS is 27.4 kg, compared to 28.9 kg without nanofluids, resulting in a reduction of approximately 1.5 kg. The volumetric footprint has slightly decreased.

Table 9 Comparison of sizing model output between conventional coolant and nanofluid for test case 5 at ground condition.

		EG40W60	0.502% Al ₂ O ₃ – EG40W60
Efficiency	[–]	0.450	0.449
Pressure Drop - coolant liquid	[Pa]	244	246
Pressure Drop - fuel	[Pa]	311	313
Massa	[kg]	6.6	6.4
L1	[m]	0.325	0.320
L2	[m]	0.325	0.320
H	[m]	0.251	0.250
Fuel flow	[kg/s]	1.3	1.3

The integration of nanofluids enables a reduction in system mass and size without requiring an increase in electrical power. The presence of nanoparticles increases the fluid’s density, leading to a lower volumetric flow rate for the same mass flow rate. As a result, electrical power demand remains relatively stable—or may even decrease—despite higher pressure drops. Plots of electrical power consumption are not reported, as no consistent trends or notable variations were observed across the simulations. However, these trends alone do not provide a comprehensive picture of nanofluid impact, and further investigation is required in the following sections.

1. Sensitivity analysis: fuel mass flow rate

The evaluation involves adjusting the fuel-side inlet flow rate, setting it to twice, 2.5 times, and three times the coolant-side inlet flow rate, as depict in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Fuel flow mass flow rate variation.

This variation in the secondary loop inlet flow rate serves as a design variable, enabling a deeper analysis of the heat exchanger and TMS sizing. This section illustrates the effect of employing these three different inlet flow rates on the heat exchanger mass.

Figure 10 Fuel flow rate sensitivity analysis: sizing model Output – a) TMS Mass; b) HX Mass; c) HX Volume; d) Electric consumption; at different thermal power level, at Ground condition.

An increase in the fuel-side mass flow rate leads to a more compact and lighter heat exchanger, due to improved convective heat transfer. However, this benefit is partially offset by the increased mass of the electric pump and associated ducting, which limits the total TMS mass reduction. As the fuel-side inlet flow rate increases, the heat exchanger mass decreases from 6.56 kg in test case 5 to 5.53 kg when the fuel flow rate is three times that of the coolant flow rate. However, the overall TMS mass does not directly follow the trend observed in the heat exchanger due to the contribution of multiple components to the total system mass. While a higher inlet mass flow rate results in a lighter and more compact heat exchanger, it concurrently necessitates a larger and heavier electric pump to sustain the desired flow rate. Moreover, increased flow rates affect the distribution ducts, which limits the overall

improvement in TMS mass across the test cases. For clarity, the heat exchanger mass trend alone is highlighted as the heat load varies. The distinct trends across the three test cases at varying mass flow rates confirm the expected proportional relationships, with no overlap between them.

A more pronounced effect is observed on the heat exchanger's volume, which becomes increasingly compact as the flow rate rises. For instance, when the fuel inlet flow rate is tripled compared to the coolant, the heat exchanger's dimensions reduce to 0.280 m x 0.280 m x 0.284 m, compared to the initial dimensions of 0.325 m x 0.325 m x 0.251 m. Thus, while higher fuel flow rates enhance heat exchanger compactness and reduce its mass, they also result in greater pressure drops and require more powerful pump components, leading to a mass-efficiency trade-off. For example, the fuel-side pressure drop increases from 310 Pa to 490 Pa as the inlet flow rate is tripled.

2. Sensitivity analysis: type and volumetric concentration of nanoparticles

To comprehensively evaluate the performance of the TMS, simulations were performed using all eight nanoparticles from the developed database. With the fuel mass flow rate and nanoparticle concentration held constant, the results reveal a closely clustered range of values with no significant deviations in the observed trend.

Figure 11 Nanoparticles comparison at same volumetric concentration at ground condition.

The performance of the TMS system is sensitive to both the type and concentration of nanoparticles. In general, higher concentrations tend to improve thermal performance, although gains diminish as the concentration approaches 1%. Among the nanoparticles tested, silver (Ag) and copper (Cu) consistently outperform alumina in reducing both the heat exchanger volume and total TMS mass. In this modelling approach, the nanofluid is treated as a homogeneous mixture, with its thermophysical properties influenced by nanoparticle concentration. Based on recommended usage levels, three concentrations below 1% were evaluated under both ground and ceiling conditions, keeping constant the nanoparticle type, inlet mass flow rate (equal to that of the coolant base), and base fluid composition (a water and 40%

antifreeze mixture). Figure 12 presents a comparison of the system performance across various nanoparticle volume concentrations. The 0% case corresponds to the use of the base coolant without any nanoparticle addition, serving as a reference for assessing the effect of nanofluid enhancement. The results show that nanofluids do not always provide consistent performance gains, reflecting the current debate in the field. Both experimental and simulation studies have reported conflicting outcomes, underscoring the need for further investigation. Nevertheless, the present analysis highlights clear trends: for instance, at 1% concentration, silver nanoparticles reduce system mass to 25 kg, compared to 28.8 kg without nanoparticles and 27.4 kg with alumina. These differences arise from the distinct thermal properties of each nanoparticle type. In summary, the choice of nanoparticle, its concentration, and the base fluid composition are key parameters for optimizing heat exchanger design and overall TMS performance.

Figure 12 Sizing model Output: Al_2O_3 – Ag – Cu comparison with three volume fraction value at ground condition.

IV. Discussion

The architecture under consideration features a liquid-liquid, offset strip-fin compact heat exchanger of the crossflow type. In this system, the primary loop transfers heat from the heat source to the heat exchanger, which subsequently transfers the heat to the secondary loop, using the engine fuel as the transfer medium. The secondary loop terminates in the wing fuel tanks, serving as the heat sink.

The initial analysis defined the primary characteristics of the TMS, starting with a heat exchanger measuring 0.10 m x 0.10 m, consisting of one layer for hot flow and two layers for cold flow to minimize local heat loss, and an initial

height of 0.0079 m. Geometric parameters were iteratively adjusted to ensure convergence as required by the model. Among the analysed cases, test case 5 at ground level represented the most demanding sizing condition, making it the focus of detailed analysis for TMS component scaling.

Under test case 5 at sea level condition, the total TMS mass exceeded 27 kg. This included 6.6 kg for the heat exchanger, 10.3 kg for fluids, 2.2 kg for the electric pump in the primary coolant fluid loop, 1.0 kg for piping, 1.3 kg for the electric pump in the fuel loop, 6.6 kg for piping, and 0.9 kg for coolant mass in the expansion tank. Additionally, the volume trend of the heat exchanger was examined, reflecting iterative adjustments made within the code to achieve model convergence.

Critical parameters include the fuel-side inlet flow rate and the type of liquid used as coolant. As shown in Figure 13, the choice of the type and volumetric concentration of nanoparticles dispersed in the base fluid can reduce the weight and volume of the TMS components, with percentage reductions of 12% and 15%, respectively.

Future analyses should explore the impact of key nanofluid parameters on TMS design.

Figure 13 Comparison of TMS mass and HX volume reduction with and without the presence of nanoparticles, illustrating the impact of nanofluids on system performance.

V. Conclusion

The transition to environmental sustainability poses a significant challenge for thermal management systems (TMS) in aviation. This study develops a parametric model to design TMS for hybrid or all-electric aircraft. The adoption of electric propulsion introduces unique thermal challenges, primarily due to the absence of heat dissipation through combustion gases. Electrified propulsion systems are typically characterized by "low-grade" heat sources, with localized regions of high heat flux despite operating at lower overall temperatures compared to conventional combustion engines. Consequently, efficient heat management and dissipation are critical for the TMS.

For this purpose, a liquid-to-liquid, offset strip fin compact heat exchanger with a crossflow configuration was developed. Simulations were conducted under five distinct thermal load conditions, representing varying degrees of hybridization. Each scenario reflected increased electric motor power demand. The simulations utilized a 40% water-

antifreeze mixture as well as nanofluids. Results indicate that the most demanding condition occurs at sea level, with a heat dissipation requirement of 67.2 kW.

An analysis of increased fuel inlet flow rates revealed only marginal improvements in overall TMS mass, primarily due to the additional mass of the pump and distribution components required to sustain higher flow rates. Increasing the secondary loop flow rate proved more effective for volume optimization. Further analyses showed that although the heat exchanger itself becomes significantly lighter and more compact with higher fuel flow rates, the impact on total system mass remains limited.

To further investigate heat transfer enhancement strategies, attention was shifted from fuel-side flow rates to the coolant loop, specifically by introducing nanoparticles into the base fluid. The coolant-side modifications revealed different performance behaviours depending on the type and concentration of nanoparticles used.

In general, increasing the nanoparticle concentration led to modest reductions in TMS mass and footprint, due to improved thermal conductivity and heat transfer efficiency. However, these benefits were not uniform across all nanoparticle types, and the results showed inconsistencies that reflect ongoing debates in the field. While certain nanoparticles—such as silver and copper—achieved greater reductions in the heat exchanger footprint compared to alumina, the overall impact on TMS performance was moderate.

Moreover, the practical application of nanofluids in aerospace systems remains subject to significant challenges, including nanoparticle agglomeration, sedimentation, and the potential for fouling, erosion, or corrosion of components. These issues could lead to increased maintenance requirements and system reliability concerns. Literature suggests potential mitigation strategies, such as the use of surfactants and corrosion inhibitors, but these require careful validation through long-term testing.

Therefore, while nanofluids show promise as an innovative solution to enhance heat transfer in electrified aerospace systems, their implementation must be approached cautiously. The potential benefits—such as reduced thermal resistance and improved cooling efficiency—should be weighed against the practical risks and uncertainties. A comprehensive sustainability assessment, including lifecycle analysis of nanofluid production, use, and disposal, is also needed to align with aerospace industry goals.

In conclusion, nanofluids may offer a complementary path toward improving TMS performance, but further research is necessary to validate their reliability, safety, and long-term viability in real-world aerospace applications.

Additionally, it should be noted that the present analysis assumes steady-state conditions during take-off and thermal loading. However, significant transient effects are expected in real operation, which likely result in the TMS being oversized. This limitation should be acknowledged, and future work should address dynamic thermal behaviours to refine system sizing and performance predictions.

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